

Fox Insight Survey Timeline

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Description

This report visualizes the Fox Insight surveys on a timeline to see when each survey began and ended data collection. This is broken down by cross-sectional surveys (i.e., administered only once) vs. longitudinal surveys (i.e., administered on a recurring basis).

The information used to create these visualizations were derived from Fox Insight [Data Dictionary \(Annotated\)](#) version dated 2024-01-09. The date used for the start of Fox Insight surveys was 2017-03-01. The sample sizes shown below are for cross-sectional surveys that have ended data collection and were cross-referenced with sample sizes reported in Fox Den.

Additional information can be found in the [Resources section of Fox DEN](#) (the data distribution platform for Fox Insight). These include the annotated data dictionary (which includes entries for each survey, including deployment and end dates, where applicable), the latest Schedule of Activities (which notes the frequency of administration of all surveys), and the survey questionnaires themselves.

If you have any questions or would like a copy of the raw data that produced these figures, please contact [Matt Kmiecik](mailto:mattk@23andme.com) (mattk@23andme.com).

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Cross-sectional surveys

Longitudinal surveys

All surveys

Sample sizes of concluded cross-sectional surveys

